

Hyperbaric Therapy in Skin Diseases

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Abstract

Skin is like a book of our life, because it is permanently exposed: stress, irresponsible sunbathing and various diseases. Furthermore, skin is a kind of age indicator. Looking at one person, usually it is not so difficult to guess the date of birth. There are, however, cases in which one can cheat the birth certificate by taking care of the skin properly. What is more, genetic predisposition and individual tendencies should be also taken into consideration. Nowadays, more and more people have skin problems. It is caused by many factors such as: food, polluted environmental, or even unhealthy lifestyle. Dermatology is responsible for studying, describing and treating the skin which affected by diseases or has some cosmetic defects. Cosmetology may be related to healthy lifestyle and nutrition, pharmacological methods, and even plastic surgeries. This field of science is quite unexplored.

Keywords: HBOT, skin disorders, warts, HPV (human papilloma virus), electrocoagulation

Originally the name 'cosmetology' concerns only beautifying human body. According to Barbara Jaroszewska this art was a part of religion and it was the domain of priests and shamans. They used a ritual makeup that emphasized their importance and distinguished them from other worshipers. Information from the field of cosmetics of that time was very precious, because it belonged to the secret knowledge that was closely guarded by the priests.[1]

Later, enhancing and so called 'beautifying' the human body reaches Chinese tradition and their art, as well as the merchants who came to Europe, especially Greece and Rome have been proved to provide essential knowledge. What is more, recipes for beauty treatments can be found in the works of Hippocrates and Krypton.

Nowadays, cosmetology has become a branch of medicine that is based on multilateral research and extensive professional literature. This science can be divided into three divisions because of its tasks:

1. Esthetics
2. Cosmetic connected with medicine
3. Cosmetic improving beauty

Barbara Jaroszewska claims that the goal of the first discipline is a reasonable care and prevention of defects, the second one is responsible for preventing defects and removing them, the third branch has the task of masking imperfections and emphasizing the positive attributes of beauty. [1] Furthermore, now cosmetics used in medicine

has become a kind of branch in dermatology. There are a lot of skin diseases that can be cured by beauty therapists. The most common example of this is a wart (verruca), which is presented in the picture below.

Picture 1. Wart (verruca) [2]

Joanna Dylewska- Grzelakowska claims that it is a popular lesion, located on a wide base that has often uneven, hyperkeratotic surface. The wart is caused by HPV (human papilloma virus) and it is usually painless, and there is no inflammation on the skin surrounding it. [3] This

skin disease can be treated by a cosmetologist. There are some methods of curing this defect.

The first and the most commonly used method is Cryotherapy. It involves the use of liquid nitrogen, which is dosed by special metal probes, cotton swabs or spray. The effectiveness of this treatment depends on the depth of freezing. During the treatment the bladder must be formed. Unfortunately, low temperatures would not damage HPV.

Second method is the laser treatment. Viral changes may be burned or cut using a CO² laser. This method is particularly indicated for the treatment of periungual warts and the anal area.

Picture 2. Periungual warts[4]

The third method is electrocoagulation. This method uses special equipment that curdles proteins in living tissues of the body. It is rarely used due to the fact that it is very painful.

Picture 3. Equipment for electrocoagulation[5]

The cosmetologist can also help patients with discolored skin patches. This affliction affects mostly women. According to B. Miękoś-Zydek, P. Czyż, A. Kaszuba, discoloured skin spots are irregular areas where changes in skin colour can be found. There are many potential reasons that cause this illness. Some of them are diseases, injuries and inflammatory problems and also unwise sunbathing. [6]

The last reason started in the thirties of the last century, because it was the beginning of the fashion for sunbathing. Women wore fitted, low-cut dresses that emphasized the waistline. Nobody hid from sunlight and they did not care about the effects of excessive tanning. This fashion lasts till these days. Moreover, there are a lot of salons called solarium where everybody can sunbath even in winter. The sun is very important for our health; however excessive tanning can also have side effects. One of them

is discoloration of the skin.
Picture 4. Wood's lamp. [7]

According to K. Prystupa- Chalkidis uneven pigmentation can be treated by using creams but it is just a way of supporting the appropriate treatment. They only dissolve pigment in the skin without eliminating the long-term causes of discoloration that is overproduction of melanin. Therefore, discoloured skin patches disappear, but this effect is usually maintained only for the next exposure to the sun.[8] How can this affliction be cured by cosmetologists? The skin treatment depends on the size of the patches. They are examined by using Wood's lamp. Sometimes it happens that some changes cannot be removed completely but cosmetologist is able to make uneven pigmentation less visible.

One method of removing discoloured skin patches it is Microdermabrasion. According to B. Miękoś-Zydek, P. Czyż, A. Kaszuba this is mechanical peel, which works by exfoliating the skin, so it can be used only when pathological changes are very shallow. This treatment might be risky and may end up with serious complications such as scarring and even more extensive discoloration.[6]

The most advanced and the most effective method is laser therapy. K. Prystupa- Chalkidis claims that laser, in contrast to other methods, works selectively. It is called selec-

tive photothermolysis. It means that the light affects only the pigment of the discolouration and misses the healthy part of the skin. Dark spots absorb laser radiation and they are damaged, so after three weeks they are excreted from the body. This causes that skin becomes lighter. The laser not only removes discolouration, but it can also reduce the number of pigment cells and it regulates the "hyperactive" producing of melanocytes. There are some kinds of laser such as Nd-YAG, pulsed dye laser and many others.[8]

Another affliction that can be treated by cosmetologists is acne. Acne vulgaris belongs to the group of the most common skin disorders. According to M. Mazur, A. Zawirska, F.Seneczko, A. Kaszuba, Z. Adamski about 80% of the population have experienced at some time in their life problems associated with it. This disease has complex and multifactorial etiology. Pathomechanism formation of lesions and its course have been fairly well known and documented. There are many factors causing this disorder such as genetic factors, hypertrophy of the sebaceous glands and excessive tallow production, increased activity of sex hormones and many others. [9] This illness must be cured by a dermatologist who can select appropriate pharmacological treatment as well as a cosmetologist who applies additional methods. Methods supporting of acne treatment may include:

- Phototherapy that uses ultraviolet radiation and its antibacterial effect of exfoliating and reducing seborrhea.
- Cryotherapy in the treatment is used because of its exfoliating effect and accelerating the repair processes.
- Laser treatment of active acne lesions is based on the use of biostimulative devices which have antiphlogistic and antiseborrheic effects.
- Chemical peels have been used in the supporting treatment of acne vulgaris. Good clinical effects can be obtained by using hydroxy acids, particularly in the treatment of acne comedonic.

Keloid is the next affliction that can be cured by cosmetologist. According to Joann Dylewska- Grzelakowska it is classified as a benign tumor with the origin of connective tissue and it is a variety of hard fibroma.[3]

An indispensable condition for forming keloids is breaking of the continuity of the skin. It may arise from various reasons such as: surgery, ulceration, chafes, injection, bites and even acne. Keloids and hypertrophic scars cause significant cosmetic defect that is often accompanied by such symptoms as itching, burning, strong redness especially of anxiety or high blood pressure.

Picture 5. Keloid[10]

The purpose of treatment is to improve the aesthetic appearance and it greatly improves the well-being and quality of life of the patient.

- Laser treatment- beam laser works by inhibiting the production of collagen, disrupting the metabolism and synthesis of fibroblasts in keloids. At the same time it causes an increase of collagenase (collagen decomposition enzyme) and the intensity of the collagen disintegration, which gives a feeling of reduction in tissue tension.
- Cryotherapy in the treatment has been used since 1974. The cold temperature freezes cells, destroys blood vessels and causes the processes of thrombosis inside them. As the result, it is the formation of blisters and scabs which in the end (after healing up) improves the aesthetic appearance of keloid. [11]

A cosmetologist can also treat angiomata, called also aesthetic defects. Małgorzata Wilk, Marcin Orłowski, Zygmunt Adamski claim they are changes arising as a result of enlargement or hyperplasia, capillary blood vessels, arteries, venous.[12] They appear at birth or create throughout life. Most of vascular lesions are associated with proliferation of the vessels, and therefore they should be classified as benign tumors. There are many kinds of angiomata such as hemangioma occurring in children, Naevus flammeus (port wine naevus), Haemangioma capillare and many others:

- Hemangioma occurring in children appears shortly after birth. This is usually located on the head and neck, after period of rapid growth subsides without treatment.
- Naevus flammeus (port wine naevus)- one side located change which is situated directly on the skin. It is quite often on the neck and face. These pathological changes remain permanently.

- Haemangiomas - it is a bright red or bluish change, sometimes flat or slightly convex, located at skin and mucous membranes of the mouth and lips.

According to Małgorzata Niemojewska the only effective method of treatment of angiomas is a laser but it can be quite painful. Short after healing there may be swelling, redness, bruising and even blisters. Therapy must be repeated several times and changes become brighter.[13] A cosmetologist can also treat diseases connected with body hair, for example hirsutism, which affects particularly women. They might grow a beard or chest hair. It is a problem not only aesthetic. Moreover there are many factors such as disease agents, which are responsible for this process. It can be also caused by certain medications, including steroids. Hirsutism occurs in about 10% of women between 18 and 45. Beauty treatments performed by a cosmetologist supports pharmacological treatment. Removal of the reason of hirsutism (eg. through the use of hormonal therapy) causes that down stops changing into visible, strong hair. However, it does not make it disappear. Local healing can consist of Epilation of electric current, laser hair removal, hair removal chemical, epilator hair removal, hair removal with hot wax and shaving. Unfortunately, the two last methods are not effective and they cause only short-term effects. A popular way of hair removal is called the electrolysis, but it is sometimes painful and very slow. Hair for hair is subjected to an electric current. The needle reaches the root of the hair and stops its growth by damaging it. The best and the most effective way is laser treatment. It damages only the root of the hair but it leaves skin cells unimpaired.

As it has been shown, cosmetology has changed particularly for the last few years. It is not only an area consisting primarily of the beautification of human body but also it is a field of the science based on deep medical knowledge of physiology, anatomy, dermatology, and particularly on the development of chemistry and technology. It requires incessant broadening the knowledge concerning the influence of the active components on the skin. It is well known that the beautiful, natural appearance can testify human health and the harmony of the whole body.

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